

TEACHING THE CREATION OF OUR GREAT SCHOLARS IN THE LESSON PROCESS

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Abstract. *The article describes the methods of teaching the works of our great scientists in the classroom. We would not be mistaken if we say that it is a great motivation to educate the young generation in the spirit of patriotism, to understand the exemplary life of our scholars and the legacy they left for us.*

Keywords: *scholars, thinker, Orient, reader, educator.*

The junior school period includes students of primary education (grades I-IV) aged 7-12. A child must be brought up in a kindergarten or family for school. Then he will be biologically and psychologically ready to learn the basics of knowledge. According to psychologists, the psyche of a child is filled enough to acquire knowledge, it differs from children of other ages with its sharpness, purity, clarity, brightness, curiosity, trustworthiness, purity of imagination, strength of memory, and thoughtfulness. In a child preparing for school education, the attention is relatively long-term and conditionally stable, especially the characteristics of the child's attention are seen in didactic games, in the process of problems, in perceiving and understanding the speech of others, listening to and retelling stories. If the child has been learning this or that information by imitating adults until the school age, now he tries to collect the necessary information of his own free will, he tries to set a clear goal and task for himself. This change in the child's behavior and activity means that his memory has developed to a certain extent. A 1st grade student organizes more knowledge activities based on vivid image memory. Speech is also coherent, expressive, and not grammatical rules, but is formed enough to exchange ideas with others according to quantity and scope. Along with this, there is also an internal (inner) aspect of the child's mental preparation for school education. By this time, he will have a correct idea about acquiring knowledge, reading and studying. Tends to obey the school discipline and follow the instructions of the teachers. But since the abilities and talents of children are not the same, important differences arise between them. As a result, some children go to school with great enthusiasm, while some go to the point of refusing school. Importantly, in school education, it is necessary to fight so that the student does not develop a negative attitude towards studying. The most optimal way in this work is an individual approach, taking into account the uniqueness of the level of knowledge in children. This is one of the requirements of the new pedagogical technology.

The term pedagogical technology (PT) corresponds to the meaning of the English phrase "an educational technology", which means educational technology. This phrase was first used by the American scientist B. Skinner in the 50s as "teaching technology". We started using this term in the early 90s. More than 300 definitions of the word technology have been given, and the widely used definition is as follows: "Technology is a pedagogical activity that includes the laws of teaching, upbringing and development and shows its final result." Based on this advanced coaching activity, it is the main task of the teacher to approach each child individually and to motivate the student to the demands of humanization and democratization of education. Although the main

figure of education in the individual approach is the teacher, the voluntary effort to receive education must be performed by the student. As a result, educational freedom is formed. In this:

1. The positive distance between the teacher and the learner disappears.
2. The learner begins to realize that knowledge is a necessity for his personality.
3. The learner develops the pride of not being behind his peers.
4. There is no barrier to free thinking, and a sense of creativity is felt in the heart.
5. The concept of self-awareness in the learner is combined with the concept of education in the spirit of universal human values.

Below we will consider the development of the lesson in the epic "Saddi Iskandari" by the great thinker Alisher Navoi.

"Hikoyat" (from Alisher Navoi's "Saddi Iskandarii" epic).

The purpose of the lesson:

- ✓ Cultivating a sense of freedom in students.
- ✓ To increase love for one's country through storytelling.
- ✓ Development of knowledge, skills.

Type of lesson: general.

Lesson style: mixed, instructional.

Teaching materials: pictures related to the topic.

- Organization of the lesson. Evaluation of Erkin Vahidov's poem "Olka" by memorization. Reinforcement of the topics covered by question-and-answer:

- Where does the homeland begin?
- Why do we honor our native land? (Through this question, a discussion is organized among the students.)

- The new topic is to tell the story from Alisher Navoi's epic "Saddi Iskandarii" by connecting it to the previous topic, using pictures based on the content of the story, and teaching the story to the students one by one, distinguishing words that are difficult to understand. , explain the meaning and write it in the dictionary: distance - road, opportunity - time, ruin - broken

- Strengthening the content of the story with the help of questions and answers:
 1. Where did the pigeon live in the story?
 2. In which direction did the pigeon escape from the cage?
 3. What did people want to do?
 4. How did the story end?
- Assess students and announce their grades.
- Reading the text and drawing a picture of a pigeon is a homework assignment

Topic: Wisdom of Navoi.

The purpose of the lesson:

- Educating students to be eager to learn, correct, kind to each other, kind, friendly, and friendly.
- Elucidating the essence of Navoi's wisdom, introducing the students to the poem.
- Development of expressive reading and memorization skills.

Type of lesson: new teacher.

The style of the lesson: mixed, demonstrative.

Equipment of the lesson: pictures on the topic, handout didactic tasks, tape recorder.

- Organization of the lesson. Asking for assessment of the assignment given at home and giving didactic handout assignments on the topics covered and getting answers:
 - card. Talk about when Alisher started writing poetry.
 - card. Find and read the conversation between Alisher and the nightingale in the book.
 - card. Talk to Alisher about Hussein's children.
 - card. What are the similarities between a poet and a king?
- Broadcasting the wisdom of Navoi to students through a tape recorder and clarifying its essence. After a short conversation about friendship, a new topic - reading Ibrahim Donish's poem "Kindness is big" to the students, analyzing the content together with the help of pictures, working with the dictionary.
- Strengthening the content of the poem with the help of questions and answers:
- Assess students and announce their grades.
- End the lesson by instructing them to memorize the poem at home and write down Navoi's wisdom in a booklet they made.

Therefore, the school is not limited to providing general education to students, it also develops the ability of independent thinking, which is a necessary condition for creative work, and the sense of creative approach to each work is formed and perfected. The main goal of teaching students is to make them pious and religious by thoroughly instilling the basics of science into their minds, to educate them to have a conscious approach to every event in social life, and to develop the ability to apply the acquired knowledge and skills to life. In this respect, reading lessons are a means of educating elementary school students in the spirit of high ideals promoted by our society. Therefore, it is important to clearly define the pedagogical issues that need to be solved in advance when the teacher is preparing for the lesson.

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